

Derivation of the Poisson Distribution

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In (1), a derivation of the Poisson distribution is given based on differential equations. The key idea is that the probability for an event to occur in dt is given by $b_1 dt$, where b_1 is a constant. B , the average value of the Poisson distribution is given by $b_1 t$, where t is some time interval. The approach of (1) is based on three steps. First $P(0,t)$ is computed, where P is probability, 0 means no events occur in t . A differential equation is developed to find $P(0,t)=\exp(-v)$. Next, $P(1,t)$ is computed (using a differential equation) and then it is suggested that induction must be used to find $P(n,t)$.

Here we compute the probability directly in 1-step using: $P(n) = N! / \{ n! (N-n)! \} (b_1 t/N)^n (1 - b_1 t/N)^{N-n}$ where $N \rightarrow \infty$.

Poisson Distribution from Differential Equations

The key assumption of (1) in deriving the Poisson distribution is that:

Probability for an even in $dt = b_1 dt$ where b_1 is a constant ((1))

Then $1 - b_1 dt$ is the probability that an event does not occur in dt . In general, one considers an interval t and (1) defines:

$B = b_1 t$, where B is the usual Poisson average ((2))

The key approach of (1) is to use differential equations in three steps. First, (1) calculates:

$P(0,t+dt) = \text{no events in time } t+dt = P(0,t) (1 - b_1 dt)$ ((3))

((3)) is solved as a differential equation and yields $\exp(-B)$.

Next, (1) solves for $P(1,t+dt)$ and then uses induction to find a general result.

Direct Calculation of the Poisson Distribution without Differential Equations

We propose a direct calculation of the Poisson distribution without using differential equations, namely:

$P(n)$ proportional to $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} N! / \{ n! (N-n)! \} (b_1 t/N)^n (1 - b_1 t/N)^{N-n}$ ((4))

Here $dt = t/N$.

Then: $P(n)$ proportional to $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N!}{(n!(N-n)!) N^n (1-b_1t/N)^n} (B)^n$

First we consider $\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} (1-b_1t/N)^n$.

(2) shows that this limit is: $\exp(-B)$. ((5))

Thus, one has to deal with the factor:

$\lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{N!}{(n!(N-n)!) N^n} (B)^n$ ((6))

We consider the case of n finite. In such a case, one has essentially 1 for ((6)) except for N^n which may be incorporated into a normalization constant.

The next case is $n \rightarrow N \rightarrow \infty$. Then: $\frac{N!}{(n!(N-n)!)} = 1$, N^n can again be incorporated into a normalization constant. Finally, $(1-b_1t/N)^n = \exp(-B)$ which also may be incorporated into a normalization constant. Thus, it seems like the key pieces of the distribution are:

$B^n / n! \exp(-B)$ ((7))

This is already normalized and so one may propose the Poisson distribution: $P(n) = \frac{B^n}{n!} \exp(-B)$ ((8))

without using differential equations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that (1) derives the Poisson distribution using differential equations and induction after defining probability for a success in dt as $b_1 dt$ and failure as $(1-b_1dt)$. We suggest that given these definitions, one may directly define probability as ((4)) and show that the Poisson distribution is present with a coefficient which may basically be treated as 1. This approach is direct and avoids differential equations (although there is no issue with using differential equations as in (1)).

References

1. Cowan, G. Derivation of the Poisson Distribution (2009)
<https://www.pp.rhul.ac.uk/~cowan/stat/notes/PoissonNote.pdf>
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Exponential_function